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Effect of addition of silica- and amine functionalized silica-nanoparticles on the microstructure of calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H) gel

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Abstract

In this work we study the influence of adding nano-silica (SiO₂, Nyasil™) and aminopropyl (–(CH₂)₃–NH₂) functionalized silica nanoparticles (Stoga) during the synthesis of calcium–silicate–hydrate (C–S–H gel). Characterization by solid state ²⁹Si NMR and ATR-FTIR spectroscopy showed that the addition of both particle types increases the average length of the silicate chains in C–S–H gel being this effect slightly more important in the case of Stoga particles. In addition, ¹³C NMR and XPS confirmed that the aminopropyl chain remains in the final product cleaved to silicon atoms at the end of the silicate chain of C–S–H gel whereas XRD measurements showed that this result in an increment in the basal distance compared with ordinary CSH. In addition, the dynamics of water within the pores of C–S–H gel was analyzed by broadband dielectric spectroscopy. We observed that water confined in C–S–H formed with the addition of nanoparticles is faster than that in plain C–S–H which can be related to a different porous structure in these materials.

1. Introduction

During hydration of tricalcium silicate (C₃S in cement chemistry notation), amorphous calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H gel) and crystalline portlandite (CH) are produced. Calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H) is the main constituent of hydrated cement paste and determines its cohesive properties. Although C–S–H gel constitutes about 60% of the fully hydrated cement paste, its structure at different length scales is still under debate in spite of the fact that this information is crucial to optimize cement-based materials [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. C–S–H gel is nearly amorphous material viewed as a mixture of tobermorite and jennite structures with a multiscale porosity ranging from the nanometer to the millimeter scales where water molecules are present [6].

In recent years, it has been reported that the addition of a small amount of nano-silica improves the performance of cement-based materials [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12]. In fact, a wide variety of nanoparticles (such as SiO₂, TiO₂, nano-clays, carbon nanotubes and Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles) have been added to cement composites. The addition of colloidal nanosilica (SiO₂) promotes and accelerates the dissolution of C₃S and therefore a rapid formation of C–S–H phase in cement paste is produced [7]. In addition, nanoparticles react with dissolved calcium ions (i.e. pozzolanic reaction) increasing the amount of C–S–H gel in the cement paste [13], [14], [15]. It has been also reported a decreasing of the Ca/Si ratio which benefits the properties of the final product. All these processes are affected by the particle size and the dispersion of the nanoparticles within the cement paste being colloidal dispersions more effective than powders [16]. Microstructural studies by area BET and nuclear magnetic resonance have indicated that Portland cement with nano-silica produce a more solid and stable bonding framework [17] due to the formation of denser microstructures through the growth of longer silica chains in C–S–H in addition to the pozzolanic effects [18]. Moreover, several authors have studied the incorporation of organic compounds/moieties in the C–S–H gel structure to improve its properties (fracture toughness and durability [19], [20]) by trying to incorporate the organic material properties as in natural bio-composites [19], [20], [21], [22], [23].

On the other hand, it is well-accepted that water molecules play an important part in both the structure and properties of cement like materials. However, the role of water in cementitious materials, or even the role of water in C–S–H gel, is also poorly understood. Water molecules are located all along the network developed by C–S–H gel: it can be adsorbed on the surface of solid phases and it can also form clusters in the gel or capillary pores of different sizes. Thus, water molecules in C–S–H gel can be categorized as interlayer hydration water and/or confined water. Different experimental techniques can be used to probe the state of water in this type of materials such as broadband dielectric spectroscopy (BDS) [6], [24], quasi-elastic neutron scattering (QENS) [25], [26], [27] and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) [28], [29]. In addition, molecular dynamics simulation can also help to understand the experimental results of this complex system [30], [31]. In previous works [6], [24], we analyzed by BDS the dynamical properties of water molecules confined in C–S–H gels with different water contents in the temperature range of 110–230

K. In particular, we found three relaxation processes related to: non-removable and dielectrically active hydroxyl groups on the internal surface of the C–S–H gel (process 1), water located in small nanometric pores (process 2) and water located in larger pores (process 3).

In this work, we report on the variation of the structure of C–S–H gel when an organic functionalization is added. Unlike in other studies where the hybrid materials were synthesized by a sol–gel process, here they were obtained by hydrating C_3S with silica nanoparticles and aminopropyl functionalized silica nanoparticles. We found that the addition of nanoparticles increase the length of the silicate chains in C–S–H gel and this effect is even more important in the case of aminopropyl silica. The aminopropyl chain remains at the edge of the silicate chains (observed by ^{13}C NMR and XPS) and this also produces a small increment in the basal distance as seen by XRD. Finally, we focus on the water dynamics of these materials by means of broadband dielectric spectroscopy. We found that the water dynamics is different in C–S–H synthesized with nanoparticles and this fact can be related to a different porous structure.

2. Experimental section

2.1 Nanoparticles

In this work we have used two different types of nanoparticles:

1. Colloidal amorphous Silica (Nyasil™ 20 – Nyacol Nano Technologies, Inc.) with a specific surface, $S_{\text{specific}} = 167 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ (mean diameter of the primary particles is 15 nm with a mean agglomerate size of 1400 nm) and pore volume = $1.74 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ according to the data provided by the manufacturer. The ^{29}Si CP-MAS NMR spectrum (see Fig. A of supplementary information) shows 2 resonances: -111.7 ppm (Q_4) and -102.0 ppm (Q_3).
2. Amine functionalized silica nanoparticles (Stoga). The route of synthesis is based on the Stöber method [32] although in this case the tetraethoxysilane reagent is reacted with aminopropyltriethoxysilane in a one pot reaction to obtain the amine functionalization. Ethanol (4 L), water (83.3 mL), tetraethoxysilane (121 mL, 0.542 mol) and (3-aminopropyl) triethoxysilane (13.2 mL, 0.0566 mol) are added to a 5 L Pyrex glass container. To this, concentrated ammonium hydroxide (39 mL) is added and the reaction is left stirring for three days. After three days, a white colloidal dispersion is obtained. The solid is separated from the solvent by centrifuge and decanting. The solid is washed three times with ethanol to remove any reactants and centrifuged and decant to collect it. The white solid obtained is air dried. The yield of the nanoparticles is around 40 g (between 35 g and 41 g). Size measurement by dynamic light scattering of the reaction dispersion, before centrifuging, of the nanoparticles was performed with a Zetasizer nano ZS (Malvern Instruments) giving a primary particle size of 150–160 nm. However, after the centrifuging and drying the nanoparticles are agglomerated. The ^{29}Si CP-MAS solid NMR (see Fig. A of supplementary information) spectrum shows 4 resonances: -111.7 ppm (Q_4), -102.0 ppm (Q_3), -67.9 ppm (T_3) and -62.2 ppm seen as a shoulder in the previous peak (T_2). The ^{13}C CP-MAS NMR spectrum of the product shows three resonances due to the 3 carbons in the aminopropyl group (42.3 ppm ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}_2$), 21.0 ppm ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}_2$), 9.0 ppm ($\text{SiO}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$) [33].

2.2. Synthesis of pure C–S–H gel and C–S–H gel with the addition of nanoparticles

Three different samples were prepared in this study by hydration of C_3S in excess of water: (a) pure C–S–H gel (CSH), (b) C–S–H gel with commercial silica nanoparticles (CSH-Nyasil), and (c) C–S–H with amine functionalized silica nanoparticles (CSH-Stoga). It is important to remark that the C_3S was added last to the water with the nanoparticles (previously dispersed with an ultrasonic probe) and therefore the pozzolanic and hydration reactions took place at the same time.

CSH was prepared by hydration of 2.5 g of pure tricalcium silicate (C_3S) with 704 g of distilled water. The resulting dispersion was sealed in a container to avoid carbonation, and after 33 days of continuous stirring at room temperature, the dispersion was filtered and the obtained solid material was dried in an oven at 60°C for an hour. Other experimental details can be seen in Ref. [6]. The resulting C–S–H gel has a water content (c_w , expressed as grams of water/grams of dry solute) of approximately $c_w = 21 \text{ wt}\%$.

The C–S–H gels with nanosilica were prepared in the same way but also adding Stoga or Nyasil™ nanoparticles. In the case of Stoga we have used 1.36 g whereas for Nyasil™ 1.2 g were used. In this way both samples had the same silica percentage. In both cases, silica nanoparticles were dispersed in 150 g of

water using an ultrasonic probe before adding the rest of the water and the C₃S. By doing so the level of agglomeration is similar in both nanoparticles (see Fig. 1b and c). The solid material obtained at the end of the hydration process (33 days) was visibly wet even after the 60 min of drying at 60 °C. As a consequence, drying time was increased in another 20 min. The resulting C–S–H gels had a water content of about $c_w = 24$ wt% for both types of nanoparticles. Immediately after preparation, samples were further dried at 70 °C in a vacuum oven (this temperature allows water evaporation without structural damage) to reach the same water concentration than ordinary C–S–H sample.

2.3. Characterization techniques

2.3.1. Thermal analysis

The typical diffractogram of a 28 days hydrated Portland cement paste [17] was obtained for the three. The thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) was performed using a TA Instruments Q500 thermogravimetric analyzer. Samples were heated from room temperature to 800 °C with a ramp rate of 5 °C/min under a constant N₂ flow of 25 mL/min. From these curves the amount of both water and carbonation was determined. In addition, the calorimetric measurements (DSC) were performed using a Q2000 TA Instruments to determine thermal events on all the samples. DSC measurements were performed using a cooling–heating cycle between 140 K and 300 K, at a rate of 10 K/min.

2.3.2. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

The infrared spectra (FTIR) were measured at room temperature over the range 600–4000 cm⁻¹ using a JASCO 6500 spectrometer which was equipped with an attenuated-total-reflectance unit (ATR). Each spectrum was collected with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and an average of 200 repetitive scans. The spectra were corrected for the base line using the software Spectra Analysis from Jasco, and no smoothing of the data was performed.

2.3.3. Solid state ²⁹Si NMR spectroscopy

The samples were characterized using the ²⁹Si solid state nuclear magnetic resonance (MAS-NMR) technique with a Bruker Advance III 400 MHz spectrometer which was operated at 79.495 MHz with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as the external standard. The experiments were recorded at room temperature (298 K), using pulses of 6.0 μs, and a recovery time of 30 s between pulses.

2.3.4. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

In this approach, the sample under study is irradiated with soft X-rays that in turn generate the emission of core electrons (photoelectric effect). The analysis of the kinetic energy of these photoelectrons allows accurately identifying the elements present in the sample, together with their chemical state. The maximum penetration depth of the technique is limited to about 5–8 nm depending on the material and the incidence angle. The measurements were performed in ultra-high vacuum conditions (UHV, pressure about 10–10 mbar) and room temperature, with a non-monochromatized Al K radiation (1486.6 eV) and a SPECS Phoibos 100 analyzer. In a first step, a survey spectrum (1200–0 eV) was acquired in order to identify the different signals present in the sample. In a second step, a detailed spectrum of the N1s, C1s, Si2p, Ca2p, and O1s regions has been also acquired. When needed, the energy shifts of the obtained spectra were corrected by using the adventitious carbon signal.

2.3.5. Broadband dielectric spectroscopy (BDS)

BDS is a technique based on the interaction of an external field with the electric dipole moment of the molecules [34]. This technique is a powerful tool for the study of the reorientation dynamics of polar molecules such as water [35]. Measuring the complex permittivity, $\epsilon^*(\omega) = \epsilon'(\omega) - i\epsilon''(\omega)$, it is possible to analyze the dynamics of the dipolar species. In the case of the present samples, information about the reorientation dynamics of the permanent electric dipoles of water molecules in C–S–H gel is obtained. We used a Novocontrol Alpha-N to measure the complex dielectric permittivity $\epsilon^*(\omega) = \epsilon'(\omega) - i\epsilon''(\omega)$, $\omega = 2\pi f$, in the frequency range 10⁻¹–10⁶ Hz. The isothermal frequency scans were performed at every 2.5th degree over the temperature range of 120–300 K. The sample temperature was controlled by a nitrogen gas flow with stability better than ±0.1 K. Parallel gold plated electrodes (with a diameter of 20 mm) were used. The sample thickness was typically of 0.4 mm.

To analyze the complex permittivity (ϵ^*), the imaginary part ϵ'' was fitted by the use of symmetric Cole–Cole functions [36].

$$\epsilon^*(\omega) = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{\Delta\epsilon}{1+(i\omega\tau)^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\epsilon$ is the dielectric strength ($\Delta\epsilon = \epsilon_s - \epsilon_\infty$, ϵ_∞ and ϵ_s are the unrelaxed and relaxed values of the dielectric constant), τ is the relaxation time and α is the stretching parameter of each relaxation process and $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency. At low frequencies conductivity effects dominate and, to account for them, a power law term was added.

Fig. 1: (a) Thermogravimetric measurements (TGA) of the mass loss up to 800 °C for STOGA and NYASIL-20 silica nanoparticles as indicated in the figure. The inset shows the weight derivative plot. (b) TEM micrograph of Nyasil-20 nanoparticles and (c) same as (b) of STOGA nanoparticles.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Thermal characterization of nanoparticles

Fig. 1a shows the results of the thermogravimetric analysis of silica (Nyasil™) and amine functionalized silica (Stoga) nanoparticles respectively. For Nyasil™ two steps on the thermo-grams are observed (seen as peaks in the derivative plot in the inset of Fig. 1a). The first rapid initial drop of the mass (from room temperature up to 200 °C) corresponds with the loss of both adsorbed water on the silica surface and structurally bound water within the silica skeleton [37]. Above 200 °C, vicinal and geminal silanol groups on silica particles are condensed to siloxanes, and this is seen as a weight drop in a broad temperature range from 200 to 800 °C [37]. For Stoga particles, three steps are observed. The first step corresponds with the release of water whereas the second one between 200 and 400 °C, corresponds with the condensation of silanol groups to siloxanes. Finally, the last step between 450 and 800 °C corresponds with the decomposition of amino groups (which are absent in Nyasil™) [38].

3.2 Thermal characterization of the C–S–H gels

Fig. 2 shows TGA results of the three C–S–H gel samples as received (inset of Fig. 2a shows derivative plot). A significant mass loss is observed up to 200 °C attributed to surface water desorption as well as water loss from C–S–H pores. In addition, a broad step in the temperature interval from 450 to 700 °C corresponds to the decomposition of carbonated phases. From these curves both water and carbonation contents were estimated and the obtained values can be seen in Table 1. Inset of Fig. 2 shows the characteristics of the carbonated phases. The addition of silica particles inhibits the formation of carbonated phases (see Table 1) but whereas the curves of CSH and CSH-Stoga show the degradation of two phases,

in the case of CSH-Nyasil only the degradation of a single phase is evidenced. Thus, the introduction of nanoparticles reduces the carbonation of C-S-H gel but this effect is more pronounced with the addition of SiO₂ particles where a complete reduction of the low temperature carbonate phase is observed. The decomposition of amino group in CSH-Stoga cannot be detected because it is expected in the same temperature range as degradation of carbonated phases.

Table 1: Water content (cw) and carbonation content (ccarb) obtained from the thermogravimetric curves in Fig. 2.

	Cw (wt%)	Ccarb (wt%)
CSH	21.24	7.90
CSH-Nyasil	21.77	2.70
CSH-Stoga	21.25	5.50

Fig. 2: Thermogravimetric measurements (TGA) of the mass loss up to 800 °C for CSH, CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga. The inset shows the weight derivative plot for the same samples.

3.3. Structural effects of the addition of nanoparticles on C-S-H: ²⁹Si NMR, ATR-FTIR, XPS and XRD results

We will first discuss the structural aspects observed in all the samples by ²⁹Si MAS-NMR. By this technique, the chemical shift of silicon is determined by the chemical nature of their neighbors. In particular, two different structures are considered: T_n and Q_n structures [39]. Q-species represent the silicon atoms bonded to four oxygen atoms whereas T-species are the silicone atoms only bond to three oxygen atoms (see a scheme in Fig. 3).

Fig. 4a shows the NMR spectra for all the samples analyzed in this work. For CSH, the result is similar to that found in previous studies [40], [41], [42], [43]. This spectrum shows two chemical shifts at -81.30 (Q₁) and -87.05 (Q₂) ppm respectively. Between Q₁ and Q₂ there is a small shoulder, located at -84.0 ppm (Q_{2B}) which can be only distinguished after deconvolution of the signal. Q₁ has been assigned to the end-chain tetrahedron; Q₂ corresponds to the in-chain tetrahedra and Q_{2B} to the bridging positions of the dreierketten structure (i.e. silicate chains with a period of three tetrahedrons). For CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil, we observe a shift of all the signals to more negative values. This shift is particularly noticeable in the case of CSH-Stoga and it indicates that the degree of silicate polymerization becomes much more important with the addition of amino-propyl functionalized nanoparticles. In addition, the lack of Q₀ in all samples indicates that C3S in these samples was fully hydrated.

Fig. 3: Schematic representation of a silicate chain of C-S-H gel. Q_n ($n = 1-4$) and T_n ($n = 1-3$) species are showed.

The components of the spectra of C-S-H gels obtained from the deconvolution process are shown in Fig. 4a and the relative area of each component (Q_1 , Q_{2B} and Q_2) is shown in Table 2. The average degree of connectivity n_c can be calculated by [44]:

$$n_c = \frac{Q_1 + 2Q_2 + T_1}{Q_1 + Q_2 + T_1} \quad (2)$$

Table 2. Area of Q_1 , Q_2 , Q_{2B} and T_1 peaks of ^{29}Si NMR spectra in Fig. 3a. n_c is the average degree of connectivity, L is the average chain length and Ca/Si represents the calcium/silicon ratio obtained by fluorescence.

Sample	Q_1	Q_{2B}	Q_2	T_1	n_c	L	Ca/Si
CSH	0.58	0.13	0.29	0.00	1.54	3.45	1.30
CSH-Nyasil	0.28	0.25	0.47	0.00	1.72	7.14	0.98
CSH-Stoga	0.16	0.29	0.49	0.06	1.78	9.21	0.96

Similarly, the average chain length L (number of silicates bound together in a chain) is:

$$L = 2 \left(1 + \frac{Q_2}{Q_1 + T_1} \right) \quad (3)$$

Table 2 shows the results of both n_c and L . The degree of connectivity and the length of the silicate chains increase with the addition of the nanoparticles being larger in the case of CSH-Stoga. This result is in agreement with previous studies on the effect of the addition of SiO_2 nanoparticles to cement based materials. However, to the best of our knowledge this is the first time this behavior is observed for amino-propyl functionalized silica. Table 2 also shows an increase in the Q_2/Q_1 ratio in samples with nanosilica which is, once again, bigger for the amino-propyl functionalized particles. This result can be correlated with the Ca/Si ratio calculated from X-ray fluorescence measurements and shown in Table 2. It is known that the mean chain length increases with decreasing Ca/Si ratio especially for values below 1.1–1.3 [45], [46]; therefore this might also be the reason for the formation of longer silicate chains. In addition, the amino-propyl group is highly hydrophilic and this could also have an impact on the gel formation because of rapid hydration compared with Nyasil nanoparticles [47].

Now we compare the spectra of bulk nanoparticles with that of CSH-Nyasil (Fig. 4b) and CSH-Stoga (Fig. 4c) respectively. Stoga and Nyasil nanoparticles show two resonances of Q-species ($Q_3 \sim -103$ ppm and $Q_4 \sim -113$ ppm) attributed to isolated silanol groups at the surface of silica nanoparticles and Si–O–Si bond in the bulk of the particles respectively. CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil do not show these Q_4 and Q_3 resonances as the Stoga and Nyasil nanoparticles do [48], which indicates that the silica nanoparticles have reacted and have formed 2D silicate chains. In addition, although T_2 and T_3 resonances are present in the spectrum of Stoga particles (T_2 and T_3 correspond to silicon units that contain the organic moiety and condensed with two or three siloxane bonds respectively) they are absent in CSH-Stoga. However, the apparition of T_1 resonance in CSH-Stoga (which does not appear in the Stoga particle spectrum) indicates that the amino-propyl functionalized siloxane groups have incorporated predominantly at the end of the chains. This structural preference of the aminopropyl functionalized silicate tetrahedra has also been observed by Minet et al. at low concentrations of functionalization (trialkoxysilane) [19], [49].

Fig. 4: (a) ^{29}Si NMR spectra of CSH, CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga. The solid line is the superposition of three peaks for CSH and CSH-Nyasil (Q_1 , Q_2 and Q_{2B}) or four peaks for CSH-Stoga (Q_1 , Q_2 , Q_{2B} and T_1). (b and c) Comparison between ^{29}Si NMR spectra of Stoga nanoparticles and CSH-Stoga and Nyasil nanoparticles and CSH-Nyasil, respectively.

To gain further insight into the nature of the nanoparticle addition, attenuated-total-reflectance Fourier Transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) measurements were performed at room temperature. The most significant differences between CSH and CSH-Nyasil or CSH-Stoga are observed in the region of 600–1200 cm^{-1} (see Fig. 5). The intense band at 952 cm^{-1} is attributed to the stretching vibrations of Si–O bonds in the tetrahedra of C–S–H gel [11]. This band slightly moves to 959 cm^{-1} in both CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga. The band at 811 cm^{-1} (due to symmetric stretching vibrations of Si–O bonds in C_3S) [50] shifts to 830 cm^{-1} and its intensity decreases for the CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil. This indicates [7] that the presence of nanoparticles accelerates the dissolution of C_3S . The broadband region from 1000 to 1200 cm^{-1} is attributed to the Si–O stretching vibrations. Björnström et al. [7], by quantum chemical model calculations, established that for silicates with increasing connectivity (similar to those found in the layered structure of C–S–H gel), the vibrational frequencies of Si–O increase. Deconvoluting the region from 900 to 1150 cm^{-1} (the deconvolution can be seen in Figs. B, C and D of Supplementary Information), we found that for CSH, two bands at 987 and 950 cm^{-1} are enough to describe the data. By contrast deconvolution of CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil requires four bands located at 1060, 989, 961, and 921 cm^{-1} respectively. Thus, the band at 987 cm^{-1} of CSH slightly shifts to 989 cm^{-1} and, in addition, another band appears at 1060 cm^{-1} . This new band, placed at higher wavenumbers, reflects the fact that the silicate chains are longer in CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga than in the CSH. These findings are in agreement with the above results obtained by ^{29}Si NMR.

Fig. 5: ATR-FTIR spectra in the range of 1200–600 cm^{-1} of CSH, CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga.

Finally, with the aim of detecting the presence or absence of the amine group in CSH-Stoga, we performed XPS measurements. This technique is very sensitive to the presence of a given chemical group based on the binding energy of the emitted photoelectrons. Fig. 6 shows a survey spectrum of CSH-Stoga, whereas the Inset shows the N 1s region. As shown, N 1s signal appears as a single peak located at 399.6 eV, which can be assigned to the C–NH₂ bond. This confirms the existence of this functional group in CSH-Stoga.

In conclusion, the structural study on these materials reveals that the silicate chains of C–S–H gel when the nanoparticles are added during hydration of C_3S , are longer than in the case of ordinary C–S–H gel; being this effect more important in the case of aminopropyl functionalized nanoparticles. In CSH-Stoga the functionalization of silica particles ($-(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}_2$) remains in the C–S–H network (XPS measurements and ^{13}C NMR) and particularly at the ends of the silicate chains of C–S–H gel (presence of T_1 species in ^{29}Si NMR). Moreover, we found that the basal spacing in CSH-Stoga increases by 1.6 Å compared with C–S–H (XRD measurements are shown Fig. E in supplementary information) probably due to the presence of the aminopropyl group. In addition, the diffraction peak becomes broader in the case of CSH-Stoga which indicates a more disordered environment.

The silicate chains look as represented in Fig. 7 where the aminopropyl group is grafted onto the end of the silicate chains and the amino group can even establish a hydrogen bond with the oxygen in the SiO_4 tetrahedra (in the silicon–oxygen tetrahedron (SiO_4)). The central silicon ion is more electropositive than oxygen and therefore there is an “electronic appetite” on the silicon atom. Thus, the tetrahedron feels the

attraction of the lone pair electrons of the amine, and it approaches causing hydrogen bonding between the oxygen (in the silicon tetrahedron) and the hydrogen atom belonging to the amine as shown in Fig. 7. This also explains the absence of T₂ in the ²⁹Si NMR spectrum of CSH-Stoga.

Next we focus on the effect of the addition of the nanoparticles on the water dynamics of the C–S–H gel. In particular we want to explore whether this structural change affects the dynamics of water in this matrix.

Fig. 6: Survey spectrum of CSH-Stoga acquired by means of XPS. The Inset shows the N 1s region, where the blue line corresponds to the fitting with a single peak centered at 399.6 eV. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 7: Proposed structure for CSH-STOGA based on structural results (see text).

3.4. Water dynamics in CSH, CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga

Now, we focus on the results of water dynamics confined in the microstructure of the three different samples (CSH, CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga) at a water content of 21 wt%. It is known that some calcium silicates react with water to give place to a porous system that evolves during the setting process, from being percolated macro-porous to micro or nano-porous structure [5], [51]. Water molecules are an essential part of this structure, being located in different environments (nano-, micro- and macro-pores, chemically bond to cement particles or even free inside the capillary pores). In general, water molecules in C–S–H gel can be categorized as hydration water and/or confined water.

As mentioned above, there are few techniques to characterize the dynamics of water in these types of systems and one of them is broadband dielectric spectroscopy. In a BDS experiment the dynamics of

molecules with a permanent dipole moment (such as the water molecule) can be probed. BDS has been used successfully to analyze the water dynamics confined in several structures [37], [52], [53], [54] and water in solutions [35], [55], [56]. In previous works [6], [24] we investigated the rotational properties of water molecules confined in C–S–H gel (39 days) with different water contents at subzero temperatures. We found three dielectric processes (labeled as 1, 2 and 3) each one related to different environments for the water molecule confined in this material. The molecular origin of process 2 is the reorientation of water molecules confined in gel pores (structural water) [6]. Process 3 is attributed to water molecules located in larger pores of the C–S–H gel (>3 nm) [6]. Finally, process 1 could be attributed to the non-removable and dielectrically active hydroxyl groups on the surface of the C–S–H gel [24].

Fig. 8 shows the comparison of the dielectric response of the three samples at 170 K (panel A) and at 200 K (Panel B). For CSH-Nyasil, we found the same general characteristics as those of CSH, i.e., three dielectric processes associated to water confined in the structure. In contrast, CSH-Stoga has a somewhat different dielectric response. In this case, we found the same processes 1 to 3 in well correspondence with the processes visible in CSH and CSH-Nyasil. However, between processes 2 and 3 we found an extra relaxation which is labeled as 2*. Thus, the dielectric response of CSH-Stoga shows four different relaxations in this temperature range. All the relaxations in Fig. 8 were fitted using the Cole–Cole function (see Eq. (1)) for each relaxation process. In both cases the result of the fitting is shown in solid lines.

Fig. 8: Frequency-dependent losses of the complex dielectric permittivity, $\epsilon^*(f)$, of CSH, CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga. Panel [A] at $T = 170$ K and Panel [B] at $T = 200$ K. The solid line through the data points is a least-square fit to a superposition of the imaginary part of one or two Cole–Cole functions respectively for (a) and (b).

Fig. 9 shows the relaxation maps for the three samples. The relaxation map is an easy way to analyze the characteristics of the dynamics from the dielectric data. For a given temperature, the frequency of the corresponding ϵ'' maximum is extracted and, a relaxation time can be calculated as ($\tau = 1/(2\pi f_{\max})$). The relaxation map shows the relaxation times as a function of the temperature. The time scale of the main relaxations 1, 2, and 2* exhibits Arrhenius-type temperature dependence ($\tau = \tau_0 \exp(E_a/kT)$, where E_a represents the activation energy and $\log(\tau_0)$ is a pre-exponential factor). Table 3 shows the activation energy of all processes. In contrast, process 3 shows a Vogel–Fulcher–Tamman (VFT) temperature dependence ($\tau = \tau_0 \exp(DT_0/(T - T_0))$) indicating that the nature of both processes (2 and 3) is different. In the following, we will discuss each dielectric process separately.

Fig. 9: Temperature dependence of the relaxation time τ (T) for the three samples analyzed at $c_w = 21$ wt%. The lines are fits according to the Arrhenius or VFT equation (see text).

Table 3: Activation energy E_a and pre-exponential factor ($\log(\tau_0)$) corresponding to processes 1, 2 and 2* for data in Fig. 9.

Sample	Process 1		Process 2		Process 2*	
	Log(τ_0 (s))	E_a (eV)	Log(τ_0 (s))	E_a (eV)	Log(τ_0 (s))	E_a (eV)
CSH	-15.2	0.25	-18.1	0.46	-	-
CSH-Nyasil	-14.7	0.24	-17.7	0.42	-	-
CSH-Stoga	-14.2	0.22	-18.9	0.45	-24.3	0.74

3.4.1. Process 1

The relaxation time of process 1 follows an Arrhenius behavior in the entire temperature range for all the three samples analyzed. The relaxation time of this process does not change with the addition of nanoparticles although the intensity increases in the case of CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga. On average, the activation energy has a value of (0.24 ± 0.20) eV for all the samples. At very low temperatures (130–150 K), it appears as an excess wing, and therefore it cannot be resolved as a separate peak. In a previous work [24], we showed that the fast process 1 could be attributed to the non-removable and dielectrically active hydroxyl groups on the surface of the C–S–H gel. This view was supported by the value of the activation energy (0.24 eV) which is close to the energy required to break a single hydrogen bond (0.22 eV) [57]. Besides, this structural interpretation is also consistent with the fact that the population of hanging hydroxyl groups increases when the C/S is reduced [45], [58], explaining why the intensity of the dielectric signal of CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil is bigger than in CSH. In addition, it might be related to a relaxation process that is observed in other systems in which hydroxyl groups are present, such as hydrated clays [59] and hydrated ordinary Portland cement [60].

3.4.2. Process 2

Process 2 was attributed to the relaxation of structural water adsorbed on the neighboring calcium silicate sheets (water extremely confined in the gel pores). The activation energy is similar for all the three samples (on average $E_a = 0.44$ eV), indicating that the environment seen by the water molecules is comparable in all the cases and similar to that found in other aqueous systems at very low water content [61]. The value of the activation energy supports that this type of water is chemically bound water. However, in spite of the fact that all the samples have the same water content and some similarities as pointed out above, the

relaxation time for both CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil becomes faster (one decade) compared with the water dynamics in CSH.

It is well-known that the dynamical behavior of water undergoes variations depending on the type of porous systems where water is confined [35]. For instance, when the pore structure is highly disordered (with a broad pore size distribution), water-surface interactions are promoted. As a result, water dynamics become faster compared with those in a well-ordered porous system [35]. This is the case of water in CSH gel where the nano-porous organization is much distorted and the filling of these nano-pores could not be the same for all the cavities in the sample. Thus, the dynamics of water confined in gels pores are largely influenced by both the solid-water interface and the distribution of water in this network.

In both CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil, the silicate chains are longer than in ordinary CSH and therefore, at the same water content, water molecules are more scattered in the interlayer space than in C-S-H gel as schematically shown in Fig. 10a and b. For this reason water dynamics is faster in CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil compared to ordinary CSH. In other words, as the silicate chains are longer and more active sites for water interactions are available, surface-water interactions are more relevant in CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil than in CSH, and this is compatible with the acceleration in the water dynamics. Another implication of this result is that the nano-porous structure in CSH-Nyasil and CSH-Stoga seems to be bigger than in ordinary C-S-H gel. This is also in agreement with a larger basal spacing found in CSH-Stoga (see Fig. E in supplementary information) in comparison to CSH.

Fig. 10: Scheme of the distribution of water molecules in CSH gel (a) and CSH-Stoga or CSH-Nyasil (b). The solid lines represent the calcium layers whereas the blue circles represent the water molecules.

3.4.3. Process 3

Process 3 is significantly slower than process 2 and therefore it arises from a different population of water molecules. As we previously studied in ordinary C-S-H at different water contents [6], [24], this process corresponds with water molecules located in the meso-porous structure of C-S-H gel. These water molecules are forming small clusters (i.e. water molecules connected by more than a single hydrogen bond) and they are involved in cooperative motions, as seen in the non-Arrhenius behavior of the temperature dependence of the relaxation times.

The water dynamics reflected by process 3 becomes slower in CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil compared with that in CSH (see Fig. 9). This behavior contrasts with that of process 2, where the dynamics become faster. This is not surprising as these two processes reflect the behavior of water molecules in different environments.

For CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil it has been shown above that the silicate chains are longer than in CSH and therefore a densification of the structure is expected [62] which in turn retards the relaxation of water molecules in the interior of the pore structure. This suggests that the size of the gel pores is on average smaller in CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil than in CSH.

3.4.4. Process 2*

Finally, we focus on process 2* which is only observed in CSH-Stoga. The main difference between CSH and CSH-Nyasil compared with CSH-Stoga is the presence of the aminopropyl chain in CSH-Stoga. Amines can form hydrogen bonds with each other as well as with water molecules. In addition, the C–S–H solution is alkaline (pH of the order of 11 or 12). At this high pH, it is reasonable to think that the amino group is in its uncharged state as NH₂ as shown by XPS measurements. We think that process 2*, is related with the dynamics associated to the aminopropyl chain enhanced by water. The high activation energy of this process (0.74 eV) indicates that we are not sensing only clusters of water molecules (in such a case, it is expected activation energy of approximately of 0.5 eV [63]).

To probe that, we also measured the dielectric response of the Stoga particles with 10 wt% of water. In this last case, we observe two dynamics: one associated with water molecules on the surface of the particles and a second one similar to that found in CSH-Stoga. Although we need more studies to probe this hypothesis, our results are compatible with the idea that the dynamics of process 2* could be associated with the relaxation of the aminopropyl group enhanced by water molecules.

4. Conclusion

In light of the experiments performed on C–S–H synthesized from C3S with and without the addition of different types of nanoparticles we can conclude that:

1. The addition of nanoparticles during the synthesis of C–S–H gel increases the length of the silicate chains.
2. In the case of the functionalized nanoparticles, the aminopropyl chain remains in the microstructure of C–S–H gel at the end of the silicate chain as seen by ²⁹Si NMR and XPS measurements.
3. Water dynamics, revealed by BDS, indicate that the microstructure of C–S–H gel changes appreciably with the addition of nanoparticles. These results suggest that in CSH-Stoga and CSH-Nyasil there are more water-surface interactions and smaller gel pores than in C–S–H.

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